

Analysis of Data Substitution Requirements and Techniques in Energy Research

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Abstract: The dynamic shift towards net zero greenhouse gas emissions, new interconnections between different energy sectors and the digitalisation towards Cyber-Physical Energy Systems (CPES) has led to novel research challenges. Modelling and simulation-based approaches are vital to address these challenges. However, tracking of models together with all data creates a complex software and data management challenges. NFDI4Energy is the national research data infrastructure for the Interdisciplinary energy system research, serves as a platform that can be utilized to identify research challenges for follow-up activities. The main aim of this paper is to enhance the efficacy of research efforts in energy domain, focusing on examination of data quality in terms of missing values and personal data privacy concerns within the NFDI4Energy platform.

Keywords: Cyber-Physical Energy Systems, FAIR Data, Synthetic Data Generation, Data Anonymization

1 Introduction

Current research on energy systems primarily rely on models and simulations which necessitate a diverse range of input data and also generate data. It includes individual software components such as energy storage system simulation models and thus, demands for research data and research data management. In the past, research data was mainly kept centralized within individual institutions, but nowadays, there is a growing trend towards increased sharing of open data and open-source software, particularly within the field of energy. Within NFDI4Energy platform, the industry partners can provide technical and business-related datasets. It can be also utilized to access existing data or services. Therefore, industry is actively involved in the development process to establish common research community services for findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) data, models, and processes in energy systems research.

One challenge that can arise here is that data shared by individual industry partners might not be complete, such as grid data including topology or line parameters that are mostly not available. In addition, it may include personal data that could reveal sensitive information regarding an individual, such as the power consumption of a household. Therefore, it is crucial to consider implementing or reusing approaches to first substitute (replace or fill) data that cannot be provided by the industry partners and second utilize appropriate anonymization techniques before sharing and feeding personal data into the platform when needed [1]. To address these challenges, this paper focuses on the analysis of the need for data substitution in research data and the identification of the tools and techniques to substitute and enrich data provided by industry partners.

2 Analysis of the Need for Data Substitution

The main goal of this section is to analyse the requirements of the energy systems regarding the need for substitute data to ensure that the platform has the data required for analysis and also that the privacy of individuals is protected [1]. Research data needed in energy system research is diverse, including real-world data collected from research projects (e.g., generation data), official statistics (e.g., a country's energy consumption), socio-economic data (e.g., economic growth or technology adoption rates), industrial data (e.g., company energy consumption), market data, and information related to critical infrastructure (e.g., grid topologies). Nonetheless, there are significant concerns in shared data by individual industry partners that necessitate data substitution in some cases. Generally, the need for substitute data can be categorized as the following:

2.1 Missing Values

There are several reasons that can lead to missing values from collected energy-related data and need to be substituted by synthetically created data. According to [2], data collection process can be affected by communication interruptions, unreliable equipment, poor network quality, or environmental influences. Consequently, these factors can result in gaps in data capture, leading to missing values that needs to be replaced or filled.

2.2 Personal Data

Personal data, as defined by General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [3], encompasses any information including names, identification numbers, online identifiers, or specific characteristics related to a person's identity which is related to a specific individual who can be identified or is identifiable. Taking advantage of personal data for any purpose other than the main purpose that it was originally acquired for, can raise privacy concerns [4]. For example, in the case of energy-related data, the disclosure of personal data such as home occupation or economic status [5] can be enabled by linking personally identifiable information with energy consumption data, which must then be processed and replaced with anonymized data.

3 Methods for Data Substitution

Considering the need for data substitution in energy domain, there are variety of tools and techniques that can be utilized for cases, where data from industry is not available or cannot be shared due to privacy concerns. These techniques can be used in order to generate synthetic data or to anonymize personal data. The main aim is to substitute and enrich data provided by industry partners.

3.1 Synthetic Data Generation

There are various techniques and methods available to generate synthetic data whenever it is missing in the original data sets provided by the industry partners, which refers to data artificially created. Such data can be taken from other data sets, such as standard load profiles or historic profiles for photovoltaic generation. Generally, the existing methods can be categorized as the following:

- Agent-based modelling frameworks such as grid topology generator [6]

- Custom synthetic data generation using packages and libraries
- Simulation tools such as PowerFactory [7], PSS/E, or GridLAB-D [8]
- Machine learning and Deep Learning methods such as k-means clustering, Bayesian Networks, Autoencoders, and Generative Adversarial Networks [9]

3.2 Personal Data Anonymization

There are various techniques and methods available to process and anonymize data whenever data in the original data set contains personal information, or allows to derive personal information. The aim is to ensure that the resulting data set no longer provides the possibility to derive any sensitive information. According to [10] and [11], the most common data anonymization techniques can be categorized to the following:

- Generalization and aggregation
- Suppression
- Perturbation and randomization
- Pseudonymization
- Statistical and mathematical methods such as k-anonymity and differential privacy

4 Conclusion

Data substitution and enrichment of data within nfdi4energy platform is crucial to establish a set of services that support the sharing of FAIR data, models, and processes for both data users and providers. Although there are variety of tools and techniques that can be applied for this purpose, the decision to either develop new mechanisms or utilize of existing ones for generating synthetic data or anonymizing personal data depends on a complete analysis of the current state and requirements of industry partners. Data types, specific guidelines, policies, legal and regulatory considerations, expected functionalities, and potential risks are some of the factors that must be carefully considered to determine the most appropriate approach.

Data availability statement

Not applicable.

Underlying and related material

Not applicable.

Author contributions

Conceptualization, F.S., Z.P.; methodology, F.S. writing—original draft preparation, F.S.; writing—review and editing, F.S., Z.P.; supervision, A.M..

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Funding

The authors would like to thank the German Federal Government, the German State Governments, and the Joint Science Conference (GWK) for their funding and support as part of the NFDI4Energy consortium. Funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) – 501865131.

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